

A narrative systematic review of young people's online mental health help-seeking experiences

Claudette Pretorius, Derek Chambers, David Coyle

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Review question

How do young people seek help online for mental health issues?

What are young people's experiences of online help-seeking?

What are the benefits of young people's use of online mental health resources for help-seeking?

What are the limitations of young people's use of online mental health resources for help-seeking?

Searches

1. Searching Electronic Databases:

The databases below will be searched with a pre-determined strategy using the keywords. limited to English citations.

i. PubMed

ii. PsycINFO

iii. Cochrane Library

iv. Scopus

v. CINAHL

vi. ACM Digital Library

vii. IEEE Xplore

2. Grey Literature

The following sources searched for relevant articles:

i. Google Scholar

ii. OAlster

iii. Conference proceedings from IAYMH conferences and Technology for Wellbeing conferences.

3. Recommendations from member stakeholders

i. ReachOut Ireland

ii. ReachOut Australia

iii. UCC Applied Psychology Department

iv. UCD Youth Mental Health Lab

v. TEAM

4. Reference searches

Reference lists from those papers that match the eligibility criteria below will be searched by hand to identify any further, relevant references, which will be subject to the same screening and selection process.

Types of study to be included

- Controlled and uncontrolled studies, including qualitative studies found in academic and published literature sources.- Grey literature- Studies designed to investigate and document the online help-seeking intentions and behaviours of young people- Studies that employed an intervention/s designed to improve help-seeking attitudes or increase help-seeking intentions or help-seeking behaviours of young people.

Condition or domain being studied

The online help-seeking of young people experiencing mental health concerns.

Participants/population

Inclusion Criteria:

- Young people not older than 25

- Participants who present with psychological distress; self-selected general population samples and those

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who have received a diagnosis from a healthcare practitioner.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies focused on a third party seeking help for the young person
- Not mental health related.

Intervention(s), exposure(s)

Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies designed to investigate and document the online help-seeking intentions and behaviours of young people
- Studies that employed an intervention/s designed to improve help-seeking attitudes or increase help-seeking intentions or help-seeking behaviours of young people

Exclusion Criteria:

- Not web or mobile application based
- Unrelated technology: computer games and their impact on mental health; social media and forums that are not specifically focused on mental health related topics.
- Studies focused on online treatment methodologies and interventions e.g. eCBT or online counselling.

Comparator(s)/control

None.

Context

Inclusion:

- Web-based help-seeking interventions
- Online mental health resources
- Informal and formal help-seeking

Exclusion:

- The help-seeking addressed was about a health outcome other than mental health
- Not web-based or online
- The citation focuses on a third party seeking help for a young person.

Main outcome(s)

- Research showing the effect of online mental health resources on formal and informal help-seeking intentions and behaviour of young people.
- Research detailing the online help-seeking experience of young people.
- Research synthesizing evidence on the factors that influence young people's online help-seeking experience.
- Research demonstrating the benefits and limitations of online mental health resources on the online help-seeking behaviours of young people.

Timing and effect measures

Unsure at this stage

Additional outcome(s)

None.

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Studies will be selected by CP by reviewing titles and abstracts and selecting articles based on the inclusion/exclusion criteria and evaluating study quality using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) methodology checklists and the Quality Assessment Tool (QAT) depending on the type of study. A second reviewer will use the same search strategy, inclusion/exclusion criteria and quality outlines to select studies. Both final sets of articles will then be compared to avoid selection bias. Any discrepancies are to be resolved through discussion, with referral to a third member of the team for arbitration where a consensus can not be reached. CP will then read the full text of each article identified for inclusion in the review and extract the pertinent data using a standardised data extraction/coding forms. There will be one for qualitative studies and another for quantitative studies informed by the NICE guidelines,

The quantitative form will look at the following data:

Reference: bibliographic reference

Study Type: cross-sectional, experimental, longitudinal

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Sample: age of participants, number of participants and gender.

Intervention

Setting

Outcome measures

Quality assessment of the study

Qualitative Studies will look at the following data:

Reference: bibliographic reference

Research parameters: research question, theoretical approach, data collection, method and process of analysis

Population: population and sample collection. Age, number and gender of participants.

Setting: setting where study undertaken

Outcomes: key themes

Quality assessment:

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

Individual studies will be assessed for quality using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) methodology checklists or the Quality Assessment Tool (QAT) depending on the type of study. This rating will be included in the data extraction forms. Quality of the included studies will be discussed during the narrative synthesis and may identify gaps in the research and guide future projects.

Strategy for data synthesis

Due to the nature of the research questions a narrative review process will be used. The narrative synthesis, informed by the guidelines published by the Cochrane Consumers and Communication Group as well as the article written by Popay et al, 2006 will be conducted once data collection has been completed. A narrative synthesis allows the discussion of the similarities and differences of findings across different studies and allows for the synthesis of quantitative and qualitative studies. Thus a narrative summary is useful when studies are heterogenous.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

None planned.

Contact details for further information

Claudette Pretorius

claudette.pretorius@ucdconnect.ie

Organisational affiliation of the review

University College Dublin.

<http://www.ucd.ie/>

Review team members and their organisational affiliations

Ms Claudette Pretorius. ReachOut Ireland/University College Dublin.

Mr Derek Chambers. ReachOut Ireland.

Mr David Coyle. University College Dublin.

Type and method of review

Systematic review

Anticipated or actual start date

01 August 2017

Anticipated completion date

29 December 2017

Funding sources/sponsors

TEAM (Technology Enabled Mental Health for Young People) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 722561

Conflicts of interest

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None known

Language

English

Country

Ireland

Stage of review

Review Ongoing

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

Humans; Mental Health; Mental Health Help, Online; Mental Health Services

Date of registration in PROSPERO

04 August 2017

Date of publication of this version

04 August 2017

Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors

Stage of review at time of this submission

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	Yes
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	Yes
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	No	No
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	No	No

Versions

04 August 2017

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